

Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity Modelling of Drought Series in Northern Nigeria

Samuel Emeka CHUKWU ^{1*}, Yusuf Martins OTACH ¹, John Jiyia MUSA ¹

Precious Oyarekhua ATEMAGBO ¹

¹ Federal University of Technology, Department of Agricultural & Bioresources Engineering, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: sechukwu6@gmail.com

Received: 01.05.2025

Accepted: 05.06.2025

Abstract

The various physical mechanisms governing the dynamics of drought series act on a seemingly wide range of temporal and spatial scales; almost all the mechanisms involved present some degree of nonlinearity. Against the back drop of these issues. This paper dealt with modelling the heteroscedasticity in the residuals of the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model using a Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) model. Attempt was made to critically evaluate the subject generalised autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (GARCH) or volatility of drought series at SPI-3 and SPI-9 timescale resolution. It was also evident that the traditional seasonal Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) models are inadequate in describing ARCH effect in SPIs series process. For instance, the squared residuals (SR) and Standardised Squared Residual (SSR) are clearly correlated and appeared to be identically same, there is no distinctive different between SR and SSR in both SPI-3 and SPI-9 as the autocorrelation structures of both squared residual series still exhibit traces of strong seasonality with a lot of Spikes exceeding the confident bounds at 5% significant limits. As the P-values of the Engle's test, as all the values are less than 0.05 significant level. The physical implication of this is that the variance of residual series is conditional on its past history; that is, the residual series exhibited ARCH effect. Therefore, the GARCH modelling approach was introduced i.e. for ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) and ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1) for the SPI-3 and SPI-9 respectively which captured the heteroscedasticity remaining in the residuals of the ARIMAs model. Considering this, the potential for a hybrid Autoregressive Moving Average (ARIMA) and Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH)-type models should be further explored and probably embraced for modelling higher temporal accumulation of SPI-12, SPI-24 and SPI-48. in view of the relevance of statistical modelling in hydrology.

Keywords: Drought, heteroscedasticity, stochastics, autocorrelation

1. Introduction

Accurate characterization and forecasting of hydrological time series are paramount for effective water resource management, agricultural planning, and disaster risk reduction, particularly in regions vulnerable to climate variability (Wilhite, 2000; World Meteorological Organization & Global Water Partnership, 2016). While the primary focus in hydrological modelling often lies on predicting the conditional mean behavior (first-order moments), the increasing importance of risk and uncertainty considerations necessitates a deeper understanding and modelling of time-varying variances, or second-order moments (Otahe et al., 2012). This time-varying variance, known as heteroscedasticity, is a common feature in many environmental and climatic processes, including drought series. Drought, defined as a natural reduction in precipitation over an extended period, often exacerbated by other climatic factors such as high temperatures, high winds, and low relative humidity, poses profound and multifaceted impacts globally (National Integrated Drought Information System, 2024). Its severity is not solely dependent on meteorological factors but also on the demands imposed by human activities and vegetation on a region finite water supplies. These complex interactions make the identification and quantification of drought socio-economic and environmental effects challenging, yet indispensable (Rafiq et al., 2023; Ponce and Shetty, 2024). In regions like Northern Nigeria, characterized by semi-arid conditions and a high dependence on rain-fed agriculture, the impacts of drought are particularly severe, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations and exacerbating existing inequalities related to poverty and resource access (Obasi et al., 2022; Gilliam et al., 2023; ActionAid UK, 2025). Given these compounding vulnerabilities, accurate and timely drought forecasting is critical for proactive planning, effective mitigation strategies, and the development of robust climate change adaptation measures (Abdeljaber et al., 2024). Traditional linear

time series models, such as Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models, have been widely applied in hydrology for forecasting mean behavior. However, these models inherently assume homoscedasticity, that is constant variance of the residuals over time. In reality, many hydrological processes exhibit non-linear dynamics, where periods of high variability tend to cluster together, followed by periods of low variability a phenomenon known as volatility clustering (Otahe et al., 2012). This indicates that the conditional variance of the series is not constant but rather dependent on past observations, a characteristic that linear models fail to capture. The presence of such conditional heteroscedasticity means that the forecast uncertainty derived from homoscedastic models may be inaccurate, leading to suboptimal risk management decisions in water resource planning and flood control (Wang et al., 2005). The Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH) model, introduced by Engle (1982), and its generalization, the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) model by Bollerslev (1986), were developed to explicitly model this time-varying volatility. These models, initially prominent in financial econometrics, allow for the serial dependence of volatility, accounting for phenomena like excess kurtosis (fat-tailed distributions) and volatility clustering, which are highly relevant to hydrologic processes (Otahe et al., 2012). While the time variation of hydrological variables has been acknowledged, the application of ARCH/GARCH models in hydrology remains relatively underexplored compared to their use in finance. Pioneering studies have demonstrated the utility of GARCH models in hydrological contexts. Wang et al. (2005) applied the GARCH approach to model the heteroscedasticity of daily and monthly streamflow time series of the upper Yellow River, concluding that conventional linear models were insufficient to describe the time-dependent variance. Chen et al. (2008) showed the superiority of non-linear ARCH models

over linear ARMA models for 10-day streamflow forecasting in Taiwan, reporting significant improvements in model efficiency and error reduction. Romilly (2005) also noted the existence of heteroscedasticity in the residuals of a Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model applied to global mean monthly temperature, suggesting the need for a GARCH model to remove it. However, a direct comparison of seasonal or integrated time series models with GARCH for hydrological variables, particularly drought indices, is still limited. Despite the growing interest in non-linear hydrological analysis, there remains a dearth of studies specifically testing and modelling the ARCH effect in Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI) time series, especially in the context of drought series in vulnerable regions like Northern Nigeria. SPI, a widely accepted drought index, is crucial for monitoring drought at various timescales (McKee et al., 1993). The ability of ARCH-type models to generate accurate forecasts of future volatility provides a better estimate of forecast uncertainty, which is invaluable for water resource management and flood control (Wang et al., 2005). Given that both conditional heteroscedasticity and asymmetric seasonality in the mean and variance can be probable sources of non-linearity (Otache, 2008), it is imperative to investigate these dynamics in drought series. Against this backdrop, the primary objective of this study is to rigorously test for the existence of ARCH effects in both SPI-3 (3-month accumulation period) and SPI-9 (9-month accumulation period) drought series in Northern Nigeria. Furthermore, if ARCH effects are confirmed, the study aims to propose and implement an ARIMA-GARCH error model for these drought series. This approach is justified by the ARCH theory's allowance for non-normality of the unconditional distribution while assuming normality of the conditional distribution, enabling the capture of time-

dependent variances. The choice of lower timescales (SPI-3 and SPI-9) for this modelling exercise is primarily due to the typical length of available monthly precipitation series, allowing for a focused and robust analysis of short to medium-term drought volatility. The findings will provide crucial insights for developing more sophisticated and reliable drought monitoring and forecasting systems, thereby enhancing climate resilience in the region.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study location and data assembly

The study focuses on Northern Nigeria, a region situated approximately between latitudes 10 °N and 14 °N and longitudes 4 °E and 15 °E. This area is predominantly characterized by arid and semi-arid climatic conditions, transitioning from Sudan savanna vegetation in the south to Sahel savanna in the north (Sombroek and Zonneveld, 1971). The climate is distinctly bi-seasonal, comprising a wet season from April to October and a dry season from November to March. This pronounced seasonality, coupled with inherent rainfall variability, makes the region highly susceptible to drought events and their socio-economic impacts (Fabeku and Faleyimu, 2017; Obasi et al., 2022). Figure 1 illustrates the hydrological areas within Northern Nigeria, providing geographical context for the study. For this research, historical monthly rainfall time series data spanning 48 years (1971-2019) were meticulously collected. The data comprised mean monthly rain gauge values (point rainfall) obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) and Zonal offices of the River Basin Development Authority across key catchment states, including Katsina, Kano, Minna, and Sokoto. Data quality control and homogenization procedures were applied to ensure the reliability and consistency of the dataset for time series analysis.

Figure 1. Hydrological areas in Northern Nigeria

2.2. SPI computation

To calculate the Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI), a gamma probability density function was fitted to the frequency of average monthly rainfall. The SPI was calculated for accumulation periods of 3, 6, and 9 months, and a detailed drought classification is

provided in Table 1. Initially, the parameters of the gamma probability distribution were used to determine the cumulative probability of the observed data series. The implementation protocol followed McKee et al. (1995) and McKee et al. (1993) and framework used is as follows:

$$G(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\hat{\alpha})} \int_0^x t^{\hat{\alpha}-1} e^{-t} dt \tag{2a}$$

$$H(x) = q + (1 - q)G(x) \tag{2b}$$

where, q= probability of zero values.

The cumulative probability gamma function was transformed into a standard normal random variable Z with mean zero and

standard deviation of one. The Z value gives the SPI, respectively. This was in accordance with recent submission of Jimoh et al. (2023).

$$Z = \text{SPI} = \begin{cases} -\left[t - \frac{c_0 + c_1 t + c_2 t^2}{1 + d_1 t + d_2 t^2 + d_3 t^3} \right] & \text{for } 0 < H(x) \leq 0.5 \\ +\left[t - \frac{c_0 + c_1 t + c_2 t^2}{1 + d_1 t + d_2 t^2 + d_3 t^3} \right] & \text{for } 0.5 < H(x) < 1.0 \end{cases} \tag{2c}$$

$$t = \begin{cases} \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{(H(x))^2} \right) \right]^{1/2} & \text{for } 0 < H(x) < 0.5 \\ \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{(1.0 - H(x))^2} \right) \right]^{1/2} & \text{for } 0.5 < H(x) < 1.0 \end{cases} \tag{2d}$$

$$\begin{cases} c_0 = 2.515517, c_1 = 0.802853 \\ c_2 = 0.010328, d_1 = 1.432788 \\ d_2 = 0.189269, d_3 = 0.001308 \end{cases}$$

Table 1. Classification of drought based on SPI

Category	SPI values
Extreme dry	$SPI \leq -2$
Severely dry	$-2 < SPI \leq -1.5$
Moderately dry	$-1.5 < SPI \leq -1$
Near normal	$-1 < SPI \leq 1$
Moderately wet	$1 < SPI \leq 1.5$
Very wet	$1.5 < SPI \leq 2$
Extreme drought	$SPI > 2$

Jimoh et al., (2023).

In this study, SPI was computed for two distinct accumulation periods:

SPI-3: Reflects short-term precipitation anomalies (3 months), primarily relevant for agricultural drought monitoring, indicating impacts on soil moisture and crop health (Chukwu 2024).

SPI-9 represents medium-term precipitation anomalies (9-month accumulation), making it particularly suitable for assessing hydrological drought conditions that affect streamflow, reservoir storage, and groundwater recharge (McKee et al., 1993; Hayes et al., 1999).

2.3. Tests for ARCH effect

The detection of ARCH effects within the drought series is fundamentally a test of serial

independence applied to the squared residuals of a pre-whitened time series. This process aims to determine if the variance of the residuals is constant (homoscedastic) or time-varying (heteroscedastic), indicating the presence of non-linear dependencies.

2.3.1. Identification of appropriate model

The detection for the ARCH effect of a drought series is actually a test of serial independence applied to the serially uncorrelated fitting error of some model, usually a linear stochastic autoregressive (AR) model. Suppose a stochastic process Y_t is generated by an $AR(p)$ process:

$$Y_t = \sigma_0 + \sum_{j=1}^p \sigma_j Y_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \tag{1}$$

There exists an information set $\Psi_{t-1} = \{y_{t-1}, y_{t-2}\}$
 $\varepsilon_t / \Psi_{t-1} \sim N(0, h)$ (2)

Where,
 $h_t = \theta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i \varepsilon_{t-1}^2$ (3)
 $\theta_0 > 0, \theta_i \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, k$

To ensure, that the conditional variance is positive. The process Y_t is called $AR(p)$ with $ARCH(k)$ errors. It is important to note that the conditional variance function might be complicated for a long series, which means that k in Equation (3), the lag of the conditional variance (ε^2), is large. If this situation exists, the computation becomes increasingly burdensome and interpretation, difficult (Otache et al., 2012).

2.3.2. Model adequacy testing

To formally test for the presence of ARCH effects in the residuals of the fitted linear

models, two primary statistical tests were employed:

1. Engle’s Lagrange Multiplier (LM) Test (Engle, 1982): This test assesses the null hypothesis (H_0) that there are no ARCH effects against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that ARCH effects are present. The test statistic is given by TR^2 , where T is the sample size and R^2 is the coefficient of determination from the regression of the squared residuals (ε_t^2) on a constant and its lagged values ($\varepsilon_{t-1}^2, \dots, \varepsilon_{t-q}^2$). Under the null hypothesis, the test statistic is asymptotically chi-square distributed with q degrees of freedom. A small p -value (typically < 0.05) indicates rejection of

the null hypothesis and thus the presence of ARCH effects.

2. Ljung-Box-Pierce Q-Test (Ljung and Box, 1978): This test is applied to the squared residuals of the series to detect any remaining serial correlation, which would indicate heteroscedasticity. The null hypothesis (H_0) is that the squared residuals are independently distributed (no ARCH effect), while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is that some autocorrelations are non-zero. The Q-statistic is defined as:

$$Q = N(N + 2) \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{\hat{r}^2 k(\varepsilon^2)}{N-k} \quad (4)$$

where, N is the sample size, and $\hat{r}^2 k(\varepsilon^2)$ is the squared sample autocorrelation of squared residual series at lag k . Like the Engle's LM test, under the null hypothesis of a linear generating mechanism for the data, namely, no

$$\lambda_t = k + \sum_{i=1}^p G_i \lambda_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^q A_j \varepsilon_{t-j}^2 \quad (5)$$

With constraints:

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^p G_i + \sum_{j=1}^q A_j < 1 \\ k > 0 \\ G_i \geq 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \\ A_j \geq 0 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, q \\ G_i = \text{is the ARCH compt} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where,

ε_t denotes a real-valued discrete time stochastic process,

p and q represent the order of the GARCH(p,q) conditional variance model;

k is a constant, GARCH: represents the p -element coefficient vector G_i and ARCH represents the q -element of the coefficient vector A_j .

Model selection for the ARIMAs and the GARCH component (p,q) was guided by several criteria based on the recommendation of Bollerslev (1986):

- Akaike Information Criterion (AIC): Models with lower AIC values are generally preferred, as they represent a better balance between goodness of fit and model complexity.
- Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC): Similar to AIC, BIC penalizes model

ARCH effect, the test statistic is asymptotically $\chi^2(l)$ distributed.

2.4. Modelling framework and development

Attempts have been made by several researchers to model both economic series and hydroclimatic processes by combining ARMA models with ARCH errors (Weiss, 1984; Hauser et al., 1998; Wang et al., 2005). The same framework was adopted in this study; here, the SPI-3 and SPI-9 series was modelled by using ARIMA- GARCH. In this regard, the ARIMA-GARCH model employed can be interpreted as a direct combination of an ARIMA model which was used to model the mean behaviour and the ARCH, for ARCH effect in the residual series from the model. The general GARCH (p,q) model for the conditional variance of innovations is:

complexity more heavily, often leading to more parsimonious models.

- Parsimony: Preference was given to simpler models (fewer parameters) that adequately capture the underlying dynamics.
- Parameter Significance: Statistical significance of the estimated model coefficients (based on t-values) was also considered to ensure robust parameterization.

The *rugarch* package in R was utilised for the estimation and fitting of the ARIMA-GARCH models, providing a comprehensive framework for volatility modelling.

3.Results

3.1. Heteroscedasticity and modelling of SPI series

3.1.1. Determination of appropriate arima model for heteroscedasticity analysis

Figure 2 clearly show that the linear stochastic models fit the respective SPIs series appropriately, as there are no significant serial correlations. Despite this though, while the residuals seemed statistically uncorrelated according to the autocorrelation function (ACF) values (*i.e.*, Figures 4.13). Figure 3

shows that the autocorrelation values are not identically distributed; that is, the residuals are not independent and identically distributed over time. This situation, basically, connotes volatility, a common behaviour of GARCH process.

Figure 2. Correlogram for (a) ACF of SPI-3 ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ (b)PACF of SPI-3 ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1) (c) ACF of SPI-9 ARIMA (2,1,2) and (d) ACF of SPI-9 ARIMA (2,1,2)

Figure 3. Segments of the Residual Series from (a) SPI-3 ARIMA (1,1,1,3) X (1, 1, 1)₁₂ model, and (b) SPI-9 ARIMA (2,1,2) model.

Though, the residuals seemed almost uncorrelated over time, the squared residuals (SR) and Standardised Squared Residual (SSR) are clearly correlated and appeared to be identically same, there is no distinctive different between SR and SSR in both SPI-3 and SPI-9 as shown in (Figure 3). The autocorrelation structures of both squared residual series still exhibit traces of strong seasonality as shown in Figure 4 with a lot of Spikes exceeding the confident bounds at 5% significant limits. In line with this, Figure 4 shows P-values of the Engle’s test, as all the

values are less than 0.05 significant level. The physical implication of this is that the variance of residual series is conditional on its past history; that is, the residual series may probably exhibit ARCH effect. In other words, the heteroscedasticity of the residuals of the ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ and ARIMA (2,1,2) of SPI-3 and SPI-9 respectively, is significant, and there is a needed to apply a GARCH approach to remove it from the residuals of the ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ and ARIMA (2,1,2) in the models.

Figure 4. Autocorrelation Function of (a) SPI-3 SR (b) SPI-3 SSR (c) SPI-9 SR and (d) SPI-9 SSR

Figure 5. P-values of the Engle’s test for SR (a) SPI-3 ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ and (b) SPI-9 ARIMA (2,1,2)

3.1.2. Application of GARCH model

According to goodness-of-fit, parameters significant and parsimony, ACF and PACF structures, two GARCH models were found suitable; GARCH (1,2), *i.e.*, GARCH(1) ARCH(2) and GARCH(5,3) models were suitable for ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ of SPI-3. Whereas, the preliminary GARCH models fitted to SPI-9 ARIMA composed of ARIMA(3,1,1)-ARCH(4), and ARIMA

(2,1,2)-GARCH(1,1).The adopted models in both instances were selected based on the smallest AIC value for each of the cases considered as well as on the basis of model parameter parsimony and significance, the latter(s) were preferred in both cases. Table 1 and Table 2 shows the parameters for the best candidate models for ARIMA (1,1,3)x(1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH(5,3) and ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH(1,1) for the SPI-3 and SPI-9 respectively.

Table 1. ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) Model Fitting for SPI-3

Parameters	Parameter values	Standard error	t-value
C	0.041653	0.033009	1.2619
K	0.583496	0.124335	4.6929
GARCH (1)	0.298277	0.114177	2.6124
ARCH (1)	0.220329	0.061153	3.6029

Table 2. ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1) Model Fitting for SPI-9

Parameters	Parameter values	Standard error	t-value
C	0.332857	0.006262	3.06825
K	0.121267	0.040312	5.91624
GARCH (1)	0.441494	0.164781	2.67927
ARCH (1)	0.156477	0.072255	2.16563

To prove the superiority of GARCH (5,3) and GARCH (1,1) for both SPI-3 and SPI-9 respectively in terms of preservation of seasonality in the variance of the residuals. The supposed GARCH (5,3) and (1,1) model were fitted to the residuals of ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂ and ARIMA (2,1,2) of the models respectively. Figure 6 shows the results for test for ARCH effect, the ACF of the SRs and SSRs ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) and ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1). Indicated no significant autocorrelation structure, in both SRs as all the coefficient at different lags are within the confidence interval, especially that of the SPI-3 series. Figure 6 shows no significant autocorrelation structure, in both standardised residual (SR) and squared standardised residual (SSR) as all the coefficient at different lags are within the confidence interval, especially for that of the SPI-3 series, even though there is no autocorrelation in the SRs (Figure 6 (a and c)), which implies that the ARCH effect has been removed, but in the SSR (Figure 6 (b and d)) there is still presence of weak autocorrelation

which is attributable to random process common in hydrologic time series. In addition, The P-values of the Engle’s test and Ljung-Box test in Tables 3 - 6 attested to the adequacy of the chosen GARCH models in capturing constant varying variance. The Tables indicated very clearly that the ARCH effect has been removed as p-value in all the considered instances exceeded significant value of 0.05 at a substantial margin. This connote, that the specified GARCH model as well as the chosen linear stochastic model was appropriate and able to remove the seasonal heteroscedasticity from the seasonal hydrologic time series. However, the findings vividly establish the fact that data pre-whitening strategy is critical in linear stochastic modelling of hydro-climatic variables. Hence, because of the seasonality of the time series employed, there is need for the adoption of deseasonalisation pre-processing approach; both of the time sequence should be cleaned via classical harmonic analysis for the deseasonalisation process so as to remove the implication of periodicity.

Figure 6. ACF of (a) SR of ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) (b) SR of ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1) (c) SSR of ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) and (d)) SSR of ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1)

Table 3. Ljung-Box test for SR of ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) of SPI-3

H	p-value	Statistic
0	0.9597	0.002554
0	1.0000	0.007535
0	1.0000	0.012112

Table 4. Engle’s LM test for SR of ARIMA (1,1,3) x (1,1,1)₁₂-GARCH (5,3) of SPI-3

H	p-value	Statistics
0	0.9612	0.002372
0	0.9998	0.005882
0	1.0000	0.008436

Table 5. Ljung-Box test for SSR of ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1) of SPI-9

H	p-value	Statistic
0	0.8191	0.05229
0	0.9826	0.31038
0	0.9993	0.39830

Table 6. Engle’s LM test for of SSR of ARIMA (2,1,2)-GARCH (1,1) of SPI-9

H	p-value	Statistic
0	0.8560	0.03294
0	0.9905	0.07922
0	0.9991	0.11509

However, it can be assumed that the seasonal heteroscedasticity may be the result of the seasonality of the atmospheric and climatic factors and components that influence the seasonal variance of hydrological variables. Based on the results, it can be opined

that GARCH that has the potential to capture nonlinear dynamics, and to a large extent reduce serial dependence and leptokurtosis, this is in accord with the findings of Otache et al. (2012), the third moment for a regular ARCH process is zero; therefore,

unconditional distributions of the series must be symmetric.

4. Discussion

It is obvious from available literature that discussions on the nonlinear mechanism, conditional heteroscedasticity in hydrological processes have been very austere. Modelling data with time varying conditional variance could be attempted in various ways, non-parametric and parametric. Towards this end, the parametric approach was adopted here. The existence of the ARCH effect was verified in the residual series from linear models fitted to SPI-3 and SPI-9 series. Following from the tests, it is shown that the ARCH effect is caused by seasonal variation. It is also evident that the traditional seasonal ARIMA models are inadequate in describing ARCH effect in the SPI-3 and SPI-9. In the light of this, and taking the seasonal variances inspected in the residuals from linear stochastic models fitted to the SPI-3 and SPI-9 series into consideration, the idea of an ARIMA-GARCH model with seasonal components is worth exploring. The ARIMA-GARCH model is basically a combination of an ARIMA model, which is used to model the mean behaviour, and GARCH model, the ARCH effect in the residuals from the ARIMA model. Thus, to preserve the seasonal variation in variance in the residuals, the ARCH model should not be fitted directly to the residual series, but rather, to seasonally standardised residuals. In addition, findings here shows the adequacy of the chosen GARCH models in capturing constant varying variance. There is clear indication that the ARCH effect has been removed as p-value in all the considered instances exceeded significant value of 0.05 at a substantial margin. This connote, that the specified GARCH model as well as the chosen linear stochastic model was appropriate and able to remove the seasonal heteroscedasticity from the seasonal hydrologic time series. However, the findings vividly establish the fact that data pre-whitening strategy is critical in linear stochastic modelling of hydro-climatic variables. Hence, because of the seasonality of

the time series employed, there is need for the adoption of deseasonalisation pre-processing approach; both of the time sequence should be cleaned via classical harmonic analysis for the deseasonalisation process so as to remove the implication of periodicity.

5. Conclusion

The application of ARIMA-GARCH models to drought series in Northern Nigeria marks a significant methodological advancement in the field of hydroclimatic analysis and drought risk modeling. By explicitly modeling time-varying variance, these models overcome a critical limitation of traditional linear time series methods, which often assume constant variance and thus fail to capture periods of heightened uncertainty particularly relevant under climate change conditions. In the context of climate change adaptation and resilience, the ARIMA-GARCH framework offers enhanced predictive capability for drought forecasting by accommodating the non-constant volatility inherent in hydroclimatic variables. As climate variability and the frequency of extreme events intensify, particularly in vulnerable regions such as Northern Nigeria, the capacity to model and anticipate variance becomes essential. The GARCH component enables a more realistic representation of future drought risks, supporting dynamic adaptation strategies that adjust resource allocation and planning based on probabilistic forecasts of both drought occurrence and its associated uncertainty. Furthermore, this approach strengthens our understanding of teleconnection influences, particularly those of large-scale climate drivers such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO). While ENSO's impact on mean precipitation patterns in West Africa is well-established, its influence on rainfall volatility and extremes is less often quantified. The GARCH structure enables the modelling of volatility clustering, thus allowing for more accurate assessments of how ENSO phases may amplify not only drought frequency but also unpredictability, a key consideration for early warning systems and seasonal forecasting efforts. The identification

of volatility persistence a signature feature of GARCH models offers valuable insights into drought recurrence and duration. The tendency of high-volatility periods (such as severe droughts) to be followed by similarly volatile episodes reflects a *memory* in the drought system that has profound implications for long-term water security and agricultural productivity. Accurate modelling of this persistence enhances probabilistic forecasts of drought duration and severity, which are critical inputs for water resource planning, reservoir operations, and the design of drought-resilient agricultural systems. In the domain of water resource management, the ARIMA-GARCH framework facilitates dynamic and risk-informed decision-making. Water allocation policies and reservoir operation protocols can be optimized based on predicted volatility levels, enabling adaptive responses during anticipated periods of extreme variability. This is particularly vital for regions like Northern Nigeria, where rainfall is not only scarce but also highly erratic. Enhanced understanding of hydrological uncertainty supports more efficient use of limited water resources, especially under competing demands for domestic use, irrigation, and energy production. For agricultural planning, the integration of conditional variance forecasts into decision support systems can empower rain-fed farming communities. Knowledge of both expected rainfall levels and their associated variability enables better decisions regarding crop type selection, sowing periods, and irrigation scheduling. In this way, GARCH informed forecasts can contribute directly to reducing crop failure, improving yield stability and strengthening food security. Additionally, the incorporation of ARIMA-GARCH models into early warning systems and policy frameworks allows for a paradigm shift from reactive crisis management to proactive drought risk governance. Rather than issuing warnings based solely on deterministic thresholds, early warning systems can now provide probabilistic forecasts that quantify uncertainty, enhancing the credibility, usefulness, and timeliness of information

disseminated to stakeholders. This shift supports the development of more flexible, robust response strategies and aligns with global frameworks such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and SDG 13 (Climate Action). In summary, the successful implementation of ARIMA-GARCH models in modeling drought dynamics in Northern Nigeria offers a more comprehensive and statistically grounded approach to drought risk assessment. By capturing the underlying volatility structure of hydroclimatic time series, this framework improves the reliability of forecasts, informs more nuanced interpretations of climate signals such as ENSO, and provides actionable insights for water management, agricultural resilience, and disaster preparedness. Future research should extend this modeling framework to longer temporal accumulation scales (e.g., SPI-12) and explore multivariate GARCH extensions to incorporate spatial and inter-variable dependencies, further enhancing the scientific and practical utility of drought forecasting in semi-arid and drought-prone environments.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

Reference

Abdeljaber, A., Oyounalsoud, M., Yilmaz, A., 2024. Scientists develop AI models able to predict future drought conditions with high accuracy. Prevention Web. (<https://www.preventionweb.net/news/scientists-develop-ai-models-able-predict-future-drought-conditions-high-accuracy>) (Accessed: 17.04.2025).

- Bollerslev, T., 1986. Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity. *Journal of Econometrics*, 31(3): 307–327.
- Chen, C.H., Liu, C.H., Su, H.C., 2008. A nonlinear time series analysis using two-stage genetic algorithms for streamflow forecasting. *Hydrological Processes*, 22: 3697–3711.
- Chukwu, S.E., 2024. Establishment of appropriate time scale resolution for regional drought characterisation in northern nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Federal University of Technology Minna.
- Engle, R.F., 1982. Autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity with estimates of the variance of united kingdom inflation. *Econometrica*, 50(4): 987-1007.
- Fabeku, B.B., Faleyimu, O.L., 2017. Drought impact assessment on vegetation over sudano-sahelian part of Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 21(6): 1135-1142.
- Gilliam, C.C., Sloan, L.M., Schmitz, C.L., 2023. Climate Change: Environmental Justice, Human Rights, and Peaceful Practices. In K. Standish & L. Reimer (Eds.), *Perspectives on Justice, Indigeneity, Gender, and Security in Human Rights Research* (pp. 301-351). Springer.
- Hauser, M.A., Kunst, R.M., 1998. Fractionally integrated models with ARCH errors: with an application to the swiss 1-month euromarket interest rate. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 10(1): 95-113.
- Hayes, M.J., Svoboda, M.D., Wilhite, D.A., Vanyarkho, O.V., 1999. Monitoring the 1996 drought using the standardized precipitation index. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 80(3): 429-438.
- Jimoh, O.D., Otache, M.Y., Adesiji, A.R., Olaleye, R.S., Agajo, J., 2023. Characterisation of meteorological drought in northern nigeria using comparative rainfall-based drought metrics. *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*, 15(2): 51-70.
- Ljung, G.M., Box, G.E.P., 1978. On a measure of lack of fit in time series models. *Biometrika*, 65(2): 297-303.
- McKee, T.B., Doesken, N.J., Kleist, J., 1993. The relationship of drought frequency and duration to time scales. In *Proceedings of the 8th Conference on Applied Climatology*, American Meteorological Society, pp. 179-184.
- McKee, T.B., Doesken, N.J., Kleist, J., 1995. Drought monitoring with multiple time scales. *Preprints, 9th Conference on Applied Climatology*, January 15-20, pp. 233-236
- McKee, T.B., Doesken, N.J., Kleist, J., 1995. Drought monitoring with multiple time scales. *Preprints, 9th Conference on Applied Climatology*, January 15-20, pp. 233-236.
- National Integrated Drought Information System (NIDIS), 2025. Drought Basics. (<https://www.drought.gov/what-is-drought/drought-basics>), (Accessed: 17.04.2025).
- Obasi, A.T., Olatunji, P.G., Bakare, Q.P., Lawal, N.T.T., Adelekan, D.T., 2022. Impact of climate change and drought attributes in Nigeria. *Atmosphere*, 13(11): 1874.
- Otache, M.Y., 2008. Contemporary analysis of benue river flow dynamics and modelling. Doctora Thesis, Hohai University, Nanjing.
- Otache, M.Y., Ahaneku, I.E., Mohammed, A.S., Musa, J.J., 2012. Conditional heteroscedasticity in streamflow process: paradox or reality? *Open Journal of Modern Hydrology*, 2: 79-90.
- Ponce, V.M., Shetty, A.V., 2024. 1. Definition of Drought. (<https://ponce.sdsu.edu/drought-hdatasheet.html>), (Accessed: 17.07.2025).
- Rafiq, M., Li, Y.C., Cheng, Y., Rahman, G., Zhao, Y., Khan, H.U., 2023. Estimation of regional meteorological aridity and drought characteristics in Baluchistan province, Pakistan. *Plos One*, 18(11): e0293073.
- Romilly, P., 2005. Time series modeling of global mean temperature for managerial decision-making. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 76: 61–70.
- Sombroek, W.G., Zonneveld, I.S., 1971. Photo-interpretation of some soils of the humid tropics. International Institute for Land Reclamation and Improvement.

- Wang, W., Van-Gelder, P.H., Verjling, J.K., Ma, J., 2005. Testing and modelling autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity of streamflow processes. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics*, 12: 55-66.
- Weiss, A.A., 1984. ARMA models with ARCH errors, *Journal of Time Series Analysis*, 5(2): 129-143.
- Wilhite, D.A., 2000. Drought: A Global Assessment. Routledge.
- World Meteorological Organization & Global Water Partnership, 2016. Handbook of Drought Indicators and Indices. Integrated Drought Management Programme.

To Cite: Chukwu, S.E., Otach, Y.M., Musa, J.J., Atemoagbo, P.O., 2025. Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity Modelling of Drought Series in Northern Nigeria. *MAS Journal of Applied Sciences*, 10(3): 414–427.
DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16478671>.
